

On the role of probability in science, analytical measurement and QUAM

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Recently, it has been shown that a probability distribution attributed to a constant, e.g., the true concentration of an analyte, cannot be used to accurately describe an objective set of information about the constant (Measurement Sensors 24, 2022, 100416; Accreditation and Quality Assurance 29, 2024, 189–192). In this paper, that result is extended to show that such a distribution cannot always accurately describe subjective belief about it either. These results suggest that a logical system of uncertainty analysis in measurement can only be based on classical principles in which probability distributions describe patterns of measurements and errors under repetition. They call into question the premise underlying the approach to the evaluation of measurement uncertainty promoted in the supplements to the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*. The relevance of these results to the Eurachem/CITAC Guide *Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement* (QUAM) is discussed, and QUAM is shown to be largely free of the problematic idea.

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Abstract

Recently, it has been shown that a probability distribution attributed to a constant, e.g., the true concentration of an analyte, cannot be used to accurately describe an objective set of information about the constant (Measurement Sensors 24, 2022, 100416; Accreditation and Quality Assurance 29, 2024, 189–192). In this paper, that result is extended to show that such a distribution cannot always accurately describe subjective belief about it either. These results suggest that a logical system of uncertainty analysis in measurement can only be based on classical principles in which probability distributions describe patterns of measurements and errors under repetition. They call into question the premise underlying the approach to the evaluation of measurement uncertainty promoted in the supplements to the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*. The relevance of these results to the Eurachem/CITAC Guide *Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement* (QUAM) is discussed, and QUAM is shown to be largely free of the problematic idea.

Keywords: error analysis, measurement uncertainty, probability, uncertainty analysis

1 Introduction

Recent articles in this journal and elsewhere [1]–[3] have considered the controversial idea that a probability distribution can meaningfully be attributed to an unknown constant, such as the true value of the measurand, θ . Willink [1] showed that if two probability distributions could accurately encode two separate sets of information about θ then, on uniting those sets of information, there would be conflicting probability distributions for the quantity $\lambda \equiv g(\theta)$ when g is monotonic and non-linear, as with the simple quantity $\lambda = 1/\theta$. The only logical conclusion to draw was that, in general, *a probability distribution cannot accurately encode a set of information about an unknown constant*. Huang [2] accepted the existence of the contradiction but asked which of the conflicting distributions should be used, calling the result a paradox. Willink [3] responded, arguing that the result was a proof rather than a paradox and that no distribution was appropriate because the fault lay in the very practice of giving a probability distribution such an interpretation. He restated his conclusion that a probability distribution cannot be said to accurately represent a set of information about a constant. This result, if correct, has severe implications for an ‘objective Bayesian’ view of data analysis.

The present communication shows how the analysis that led to that result can be extended to apply to the subjective Bayesian understanding of probability also. We are led to the conclusion that a continuous probability distribution attributed to *a constant* does not necessarily satisfy the principles of logic, no matter how it is interpreted.

From this conclusion, it follows that the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM) [4, 5] should not be interpreted in such a way – as it is in recent supplementary material to the GUM, e.g., [6, 7]. Rather, any interpretation or extension of the GUM must follow classical lines. This claim is of relevance to the Eurachem/CITAC Guide “Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement” (QUAM) [8], which describes a method of analysis that is consistent with a classical reading of the (original) GUM, but which contains some peripheral clauses that appeal to the problematic concept.

Section 2 demonstrates the result for objective probability and Section 3 extends the result to apply to subjective probability. Section 4 briefly discusses the position taken in official documents that have been developed to build on the GUM, and Section 5 examines in more detail the contrasting approach taken in QUAM, upholding that approach but providing cautionary comments.

2 Analysis for distributions representing information about constants

The objective Bayesian position in which probability represents “rational belief” is based on the following premise. “*From any set of information, i.e., set of facts, relating to a quantity, there is a unique pdf to attribute to that quantity*”, e.g., [9, pp. 9,10]. So let us imagine that unknown constant quantities θ_1 and θ_2 exist, that you accept the premise, and that you attribute probability density functions (pdfs) $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ to θ_1 and θ_2 to accurately represent disjoint sets of information about them, say the sets S_1 and S_2 . Let $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ be the values of θ_1 and θ_2 when rounded onto a discrete scale with potential values $\dots -2\delta, -\delta, 0, \delta, 2\delta, \dots$, and let $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ be the corresponding probability mass functions (pmfs). (So $p_j(x) = \int_{x-\delta/2}^{x+\delta/2} f_j(z)dz$.) Then, in your thinking, $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are independent

discrete random variables with pmfs $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$, these variables being independent because the sets of information that they describe, S_1 and S_2 , are disjoint. The corresponding joint pmf is

$$\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2) = p_1(x_1)p_2(x_2).$$

This is exemplified in Figure 1(a) for $\delta = 1$ with $(p_1(2), p_1(3), p_1(4), p_1(5), p_1(6)) = (0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1)$ and $(p_2(1), p_2(2), p_2(3), p_2(4), p_2(5)) = (0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1)$.

Figure 1: (a) Example joint probability mass function $\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2)$ with $\delta = 1$. (b) Corresponding probability mass function on the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$. (Empty cells have mass zero.)

Recall that the probability that event A occurs on the condition that event B occurs is $\Pr(A|B) = \Pr(A \cap B) / \Pr(B)$. Now suppose that you receive the single new piece of information that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal, which is a single piece of information constituting a set S_3 . So you learn that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal. On the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$, the probability that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ have different values is zero and the probability that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal to any dummy figure x is seen to be

$$\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2 = x \mid \hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2) = \frac{p_1(x)p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z)p_2(z)},$$

which is a quantity that involves only the diagonal elements of the array of joint probabilities, as depicted in Figure 1(b) for the unconditional distribution of Figure 1(a). There is now only one unknown quantity, which we can rename θ , with the discretized form being $\hat{\theta}$. We find that, after this new piece

of information has been accommodated, you must regard $\hat{\theta}$ as a discrete random variable with pmf

$$p(x) = \frac{p_1(x) p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z) p_2(z)}. \quad (1)$$

It makes no difference to your final set of information about $\hat{\theta}$ whether you learn that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal before or after you are provided with the two sets of information S_1 and S_2 , i.e., it makes no difference to your final set of information $S_{\text{final}} \equiv S_1 \cup S_2 \cup S_3$ whether you receive S_3 first or last. So (1) must also represent the correct combination of pmfs $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ that are said to correspond to two disjoint sets of information about a single quantity, $\hat{\theta}$.

Equation (1) can be written as

$$\frac{p(x)}{\delta} = \frac{p_1(x)/\delta \times p_2(x)/\delta}{\sum_z p_1(z)/\delta \times p_2(z)/\delta \times \delta},$$

and this equation holds whatever the value of the unit of resolution, δ . As δ is reduced to zero, $\hat{\theta}$ becomes θ , $p_j(\cdot)/\delta$ becomes $f_j(\cdot)$, $p(\cdot)/\delta$ becomes a combined pdf $f(\cdot)$, and the sum becomes an integral. This gives the expression

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x)}{\int f_1(z)f_2(z) dz} \quad (2)$$

as the unique equation describing the result when two independently-formed objective pdfs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ for a single constant are to be logically combined.

Let us now use a subscript in the pdf to identify the quantity of interest, e.g., θ . The analysis that has led to (2) has proven the following result: if $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ are the pdfs to attribute to a quantity θ to accurately represent two disjoint sets of information about θ then the pdf to accurately represent the union of the sets of information obeys [1, Sec. 3.2], e.g., [10, Eqs. 5,6][11, Eq. 15]

$$f_{12\theta}(x) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x). \quad (3)$$

(The proportionality constant is such that the integral of $f_{12\theta}(x)$ is 1.) Now suppose that the particular quantity of interest is $\lambda = g(\theta)$, where g is a monotonic function. As is well known, if the pdf attributed to θ is $f_\theta(x)$ then the pdf attributed to λ must be

$$f_\lambda(y) = f_\theta(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right| \quad y = g(x). \quad (4)$$

So, if there are two disjoint sets of information then the pdf attributable to λ will be found from the input pdfs $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ in two stages by applying equations of the ‘combination’ form (3) and the ‘transformation’ form (4). These operations simply represent logical reasoning with summable sets of information — so it is legitimate to combine first and then transform and it is also legitimate to transform first and then combine: the result must be the same because all that is being carried out is the aggregation and re-expression of information.

Combining the two pdfs before transforming from θ to λ gives the intermediate result (3) and the final pdf

$$f_{12\lambda}(y) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (5)$$

but transforming to λ before combining gives the intermediate result $f_{j\lambda}(y) = f_{j\theta}(x) |dx/dy|$ for $j = 1, 2$ and the final pdf

$$f_{12\lambda}(y) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|^2, \quad (6)$$

in which the Jacobian $|dx/dy|$ is raised to the power of 2, (because there are two contributing pdfs). The pdfs (5) and (6) differ if g is non-linear, as with the simple relationship $\lambda = 1/\theta$. Yet both are obtained from our premise and from correct use of probability theory. It follows that the premise that a set of information can be accurately encoded as a probability distribution leads to an internal inconsistency [1, Sec. 3.3]. Therefore, this premise must be incorrect. We conclude that a probability distribution for a constant does not accurately represent *a set of information* about it, i.e., a set of facts relating to it. This is the conclusion emphasized in the earlier publications [1, 3].

3 Extension to distributions representing subjective belief about constants

Now let us consider whether the assignment of a (continuous) probability distribution to a constant can instead accurately represent *subjective belief* about it. So let $f_{1\theta}(x)$ now be your subjective pdf for an unknown quantity, say the diameter θ of a specific disk. According to Bayesian reasoning, this pdf can be formed by any thought process that you like: all that is required is that it honestly represents your belief about θ based on all that you consider relevant. Suppose that *after* forming $f_{1\theta}(x)$ you are told by some external party that the disk was drawn at random from a production line that created disks with diameters following a frequency distribution with a density $g(x)$. Taken in isolation, this so-far unused impression or piece of information would have led to you to form some pdf of belief, $f_{2\theta}(x)$, from it. (The form of $f_{2\theta}(x)$ is not important to this argument, but surely a person who fully trusted what they had been told would have assigned θ the pdf $f_{2\theta}(x) = g(x)$.) The two pdfs $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ are derived from independent (disjoint, separate) influences — and they can also be interpreted as pdfs for two quantities that are subsequently found to be the same, exactly as in the argument in Section 2. So when combining these two pdfs to express your final belief about θ you must form the product $f_{12\theta}(x) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x)$, as above. Then the same inconsistency arises when, for example, you study the area of the disk $\lambda = \pi\theta^2/4$ as well as its diameter θ .

Thus, we are forced to the conclusion that, in general, attributing a *subjective* probability distribution to a constant also admits a logical contradiction. So, it appears that the basis of Bayesian statistical analysis is illogical. For that conclusion to be denied, the analysis that has just been given must itself be shown to be incorrect.

4 Supplements to the “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement”

Our discussion has been about reasoning with probability in science. The material might seem academic and irrelevant to those who only use probability for its classical task of describing the frequency behaviour of unpredictable processes. However, current international guidelines in measurement science adopt the position that probability distributions are (also) to be given to constants, as in Bayesian analysis. For example, in a document of 2009 [6, 3.17] that claims to introduce the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM) of 1995 [4, 5] we read

The true values of the input quantities ... are unknown. In the approach advocated, [the input quantities] are characterized by probability distributions ... and treated mathematically as random variables These distributions describe the respective probabilities of their true values lying in different intervals, and are assigned based on available knowledge concerning [the input quantities].

and in the first supplement to the GUM from 2008 we read [7, Introduction]:

The PDF for a quantity expresses the state of knowledge about the quantity, i.e. it quantifies the degree of belief about the values that can be assigned to the quantity based on the available information.

The relevant concept is that a constant, e.g., the true value of the measurand, is being attributed a probability distribution. Accordingly, we can read in related material [12, 3b]

A probability distribution (on the set of possible values of the measurand) provides a complete characterization of measurement uncertainty ...

The inescapable conclusion is that guidelines recently issued to clarify and extend the GUM have adopted a premise that is logically inconsistent. This implies that they cannot possibly lead to a coherent universal system of analysis. Perhaps more importantly, it means that the system currently advocated for the analysis of measurement uncertainty in science is founded on an unscientific misconception.

5 Eurachem/CITAC Guide — “Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement”

Our subject is the notion of attributing a probability distribution to an unknown constant. In the context of metrology, this has been called the ‘distributed measurand’ concept [13], but here we will call it the ‘distributed-constant idea’. It remains to comment on the relationship of this idea to the current edition of QUAM [8]. Our conclusion will be that, to a large extent, QUAM avoids the logical error that has been outlined. However, by the peripheral inclusion of some related material, QUAM endangers its scientific position.

5.1 Classical and neo-classical ideas

In the context of statistical analysis, QUAM begins with a statement of classical ideas. We read

2.3.3. ... The expanded uncertainty provides an interval within which the value of the measurand is believed to lie with a higher level of confidence.

The use of the word ‘confidence’ implies the adoption of the classical approach, though clearer wording would be ‘is believed with a higher level of confidence to lie’. If the distributed-constant idea had been adopted then the most appropriate word here would have been ‘probability’ and it would have appeared in the phrase ‘is believed to lie with a higher probability’.

So QUAM uses classical language, where the concept of confidence is associated with an interval obtained using a well-defined repeatable procedure. Accordingly we read

2.4.2. Uncertainty, on the other hand, takes the form of a range or interval, and, if estimated for an analytical procedure and defined sample type, may apply to all determinations so described. ...

The fact that uncertainty is assessed *for an analytical procedure* and *for all determinations* places the emphasis on variability in the data-generating process, not on doubt about the specific measurand. So, for QUAM, uncertainty is primarily determined by the procedure; in contrast, the distributed-constant idea makes the uncertainty a property of the specific measurand. (See QUAM 7.3 where the focus is on procedure.) Also, the fact that uncertainty is said to be ‘estimated’ implies that it is something objective and unknown. (See also QUAM section 4). If the distributed-constant idea applied then the uncertainty would be fully known because it would simply describe one’s own state of mind about the true value of the measurand.

In accordance with these ideas, the distributions that QUAM describes are distributions of data, whether observable in repeatable measurements or unobservable via a concept of belief [8, 7.15.5, 7.15.6], not distributions assigned to constants. Under the heading ‘Estimation based on judgement’, we read

7.15.2. Most distributions of data can be interpreted in the sense that it is less likely to observe data in the margins of the distribution than in the centre. The quantification of these distributions and their associated standard deviations is done through repeated measurements.

and then

7.15.9. For the purpose of estimation of combined uncertainties two features of degree of belief estimations are essential:

- degree of belief is regarded as interval valued which is to say that a lower and an upper bound similar to a classical probability distribution is provided,
- the same computational rules apply in combining ‘degree of belief’ contributions of uncertainty to a combined uncertainty as for standard deviations derived by other methods.

There is no mention of ‘standard deviation’ in the material between these two clauses, so the standard deviations of the degree-of-belief contributions being combined in 7.15.9 are as standard deviations for data (e.g., measurements) in 7.15.2, not as standard deviations describing belief about constants. In keeping with this we read

7.15.7. This may appear to be a disadvantage, but need not lead in practice to worse estimates than those from repeated measurements. This applies particularly if the true, real-life, variability in experimental conditions cannot be simulated and the resulting variability in data thus does not give a realistic picture.

The quotations that have just been given illustrate the key point: QUAM understands uncertainty to be about variability under repetition, and where actual repetition is not practical it appeals to the concept of degree of belief about variability, not degree of belief about a constant. So, QUAM upholds a degree-of-belief concept, but the subject of the belief is the error in a potential measurement of a fixed measurand, the subject of the belief is not the actual value of that measurand.

This approach is also seen in the next section, which is entitled ‘Standard uncertainties’

8.1.2. Where the uncertainty component was evaluated experimentally from the dispersion of repeated measurements, it can readily be expressed as a standard deviation. For the contribution to uncertainty in single measurements, the standard uncertainty is simply the observed standard deviation; for results subjected to averaging, the **standard deviation of the mean** ... is used.

and

8.1.6. Where an estimate is to be made on the basis of judgement, it may be possible to estimate the component directly as a standard deviation. If this is not possible then an estimate should be made of the maximum deviation which could reasonably occur in practice (excluding simple mistakes). If a smaller value is considered substantially more likely, this estimate should be treated as descriptive of a triangular distribution. If there are no grounds for believing that a small error is more likely than a large error, the estimate should be treated as characterising a rectangular distribution.

The phrase “the maximum deviation which could reasonably occur in practice” shows that QUAM has in mind a distribution corresponding to the generation of data (with errors) in a measurement procedure.

So QUAM upholds a degree-of-belief concept for a potential measurement or a potential error in a measurement, but (in the body of its text) it does not use the degree-of-belief concept employed by Bayesian statisticians, which is the concept that each unknown constant is to be attributed a probability distribution, i.e., the distributed-constant idea. In this way, QUAM is conceptually consistent with a neo-classical method of analysis recently developed to be true to foundational principles [14], including the report [15] containing Recommendation INC-1 [4, 0.7], where Type B evaluation of uncertainty was formally recommended. (The term ‘neo-classical’ seems appropriate because the ‘Type B’ recommendation that variances and probability distributions can be associated with systematic errors constitutes a departure from the classical approach as perceived by statisticians [16].)

5.2 Distributed-constant idea

However, QUAM also briefly refers to some ideas and principles found in the supplements to the GUM, which are inconsistent with the classical ideas above and which we have demonstrated are logically flawed. To show this, we make clear the meaning of the term ‘input quantity’. In Clause 4.1, QUAM considers various steps in the problem of assessing the uncertainty in measurement. We read

Step 1. Specify measurand

Write down a clear statement of what is being measured, including the relationship between the measurand and the input quantities (*e.g.* measured quantities, constants, calibration standard values *etc.*) upon which it depends. ...

This confirms that QUAM sees an *input quantity* as having the nature of a measurand, not the nature of a potential measurement. (Indeed, there is explicit mention of constants potentially being input quantities.) So an input quantity has an unknown true value, and to attribute it a probability distribution would be to abandon the classical statistical approach and to adopt the distributed-constant idea. This is relevant, because in Appendix E.3, which is new to the third edition, we then find text that presumes acceptance of the distributed-constant idea. In Clause E.3.2 we read

Monte Carlo Simulation calculates the result corresponding to one value of each input quantity drawn at random from its PDF, and repeats this calculation a large number of times (trials), typically 10^5 to 10^6 . This process produces a set of simulated results which, under certain assumptions, forms an approximation to the PDF for the value of the measurand. From this set of simulated results, the mean value and standard deviation are calculated. In GUM Supplement 1, these are used respectively as the estimate of the measurand and the standard uncertainty associated with this estimate. ...

We read of input quantities having PDFs, the value of the measurand having a PDF, the mean (of this PDF) being the estimate of the measurand, and the standard deviation (of this PDF) being the corresponding standard uncertainty. So, Appendix E.3 describes the distributed-constant idea, which is not compatible with the classical approach found in the remainder of QUAM. Thus, any positive reference in the body of QUAM to the technique of analysis in Appendix E.3 can only introduce confusion. Moreover, as shown earlier in this article, the distributed-constant idea is not logically sound!

5.3 Comments

This section has demonstrated that the statistical and probabilistic material in the body of QUAM relates to distributions of estimates or distributions of errors in estimates, as was initially envisaged for Type B evaluation [15, 16]. Yet QUAM would claim compatibility with the GUM. So there is evidence that the writers of QUAM and the writers of the supplements to the GUM have interpreted the original GUM differently. The writers of QUAM have (almost entirely) avoided considering the measurand to have a distribution, whereas the writers of the supplements to the GUM, who form Working Group 1 of the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (WG1), expressly base their methodology and recommendations upon that idea. In QUAM, a degree-of-belief concept is applied to estimates in

a manner that is consistent with a neo-classical form of analysis described recently [14]. But in the material prepared by WG1, the degree-of-belief concept is applied to constants. So if QUAM continues to claim compatibility with the GUM while WG1 continues to produce new material that is said to form part of “the GUM” then QUAM will be seen to be accepting an illogical basis for its system of analysis. This should be a matter of concern.

6 Conclusions

The practice of attributing a probability distribution to an entity to describe belief about it arises in Type B evaluation of measurement uncertainty. But this practice is fundamentally different for parties who consider different types of entity. For those who adhere to a classical or neo-classical approach, the entity will be the future output of a measurement procedure, be it a future datum or the error in the future datum, as was originally envisaged [15]. Then the distribution describing degree-of-belief will be little more than a standard model for the generation of an error, the only difference being an inability to test the model by repetition of the experiment. But for those who adhere to the Bayesian view of statistics, the entity will usually be an unknown constant, as in the distributed-constant idea. So the legitimacy of a ‘degree of belief’ is not being criticized here: rather, it is the breadth of its applicability.

Accordingly, this paper has built on earlier papers [1, 3] to give a succinct demonstration that, in general, attributing a probability distribution to a constant to describe your belief about it admits a logical contradiction. The result appears to invalidate the Bayesian view of data analysis, so it demands acceptance or rebuttal. It is a result that urgently needs to be disproven if guidelines in metrology are to continue to adopt the premise that probability distributions can be attributed to measurands. The guidelines of concern are those prepared by Working Group 1 of the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, which has produced a suite of documents claiming to build on the GUM of 1993/1995, e.g., [6, 7]. By and large, the current edition of QUAM avoids the problem and continues to base its method on the classical understanding that probability distributions relate to the spread of data or observations. A future edition of QUAM should distance itself further from the illogical premise.

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